

GIANT PERIPHERAL SCHWANNOMA WITH EXTENSIVE CYSTIC AND HEMORRHAGIC CHANGE

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Abstract

A 53 year old male patient presented to the out-patient department of General Surgery with complaints of swelling over right thigh. The ultrasound findings were consistent with a Parasitic cyst. FNAC showed scanty spindle cells on a background of hemorrhage. Complete excision was done and sent for histopathology, where it was diagnosed as Schwannoma with extensive cystic and hemorrhagic change. This case report is unusual for its extensive secondary changes.

Keywords: Schwannoma, Thigh lesions, FNAC, Cystic and hemorrhagic change, Perls stain.

Introduction

Peripheral schwannoma is a slow growing, encapsulated, usually solitary, benign nerve sheath tumor arising from differentiated Schwann cells.[1]

Case Report:

A 53 year old male patient presented to the General Surgery out-patient department with a gradually increasing swelling over right thigh noticed since two months and having pain in the swelling since ten days (Figure 1a). On examination, a swelling of 6x3x3 cm was seen on lateral aspect of upper one-third of right thigh. The overlying skin was normal, without any ulceration discharge or skin changes. It was soft to cystic in consistency, non-tender and slightly mobile, more so horizontally than vertically. There was no inguinal lymphadenopathy. A provisional diagnosis of Benign Cystic and/or Soft tissue lesion was made. The ultrasound report was indicative of a parasitic cyst. Fine needle aspiration cytology was done which showed paucicellular smears with a few bland spindle cells on a background of RBC and was opined as a benign spindle cell neoplasm. (Figure 2)

Routine investigations were done and were within normal limits. The swelling was excised under regional/ spinal anesthesia. Intraoperatively, it was an intramuscular swelling and was excised in toto (Figure 1b).

On Histopathology (Figure 3, 4): On gross examination, a greyish, well-circumscribed nodular mass of 6x4x4 cm was seen. The cut surface showed central cystic area completely filled with hemorrhage with a peripheral rim of preserved greyish tissue. On clearing the blood, the inner surface was uniformly greyish and smooth (Figure 3a).

On microscopy (Figure 3) of the preserved areas, features of Schwannoma were seen with mostly cellular areas ie Antoni A areas, composed of short plump spindled cells were observed along with a few Verocay bodies. The hypocellular ie Antoni B areas showed myxoid matrix. Perivascular hyalinisation was prominently seen. There were many singly scattered and clusters of

hemosiderin-laden macrophages. This was confirmed by Perl's stain for iron (Figure 4). There was no necrosis, mitoses or atypia. Confirmatory immunohistochemistry with S100 stain was not done in this case.

All the surgical margins were free from tumor.

The patient's post-operative recovery was uneventful and the patient was symptom-free at annual follow-up.

Discussion

Schwannomas are also known as neurilemmomas, and are the most common peripheral nerve sheath tumors that arise from differentiated Schwann cells. They affect all age groups and peripheral schwannomas are more common from 30 through 60 years age. Peripheral nerve sheath tumors account for less than 8% of soft tissue neoplasms. [2] They are more common in the extremities and about 32.6 % of schwannomas arise in the extremities. [3,4] Schwannomas are solitary, isolated, well-capsulated and sporadic in 90 % of cases while 10 % of schwannomas can occur at multiple sites. Multiple schwannomas are usually due to genetic abnormalities such as neurofibromatosis type 2, Schwannomatosis, and Carney complex. [5] The size of schwannomas ranges from 2 cm to 20 cm and most of them are smaller than 5 cm. Those greater than 5 cm are called Giant schwannomas. [6]

The central nervous system schwannomas behave as World Health Organization (WHO) grade I tumors, and only very rarely undergo malignant transformation. Loss of function of merlin, either by direct genetic change involving the NF2 gene on chromosome 22 or secondarily to merlin inactivation is thought to play an important role in the pathogenesis of schwannomas. [1] Grossly, schwannomas are usually solitary, well-circumscribed, firm, smooth surfaced tumors. The extracranial schwannomas are usually large, and may have secondary degenerative changes due to the long duration resulting in the increase and decrease in the tumor size. [7] Degenerative changes such as hemorrhage, calcification, and fibrosis are common in schwannoma, but cystic changes are rare. [8] Degeneration is due to

central tumor necrosis as the schwannoma outstrips its blood supply.[7] Such schwannomas may show numerous siderophages.[8] Lim JH reported a case of Schwannoma in a 63 year old woman which presented as a purely hemorrhagic cystic lesion in right thigh.[9] Our patient had a history of pain in the swelling since ten days which could be attributed to spontaneous hemorrhage.

There are some distinct variants of Schwannoma like Cellular schwannomas, Plexiform type, Melanotic type, Ancient schwannoma. They rarely undergo malignant transformation and it often acquires an epithelioid or primitive neuroectodermal morphology. Whereas, when a neurofibroma undergoes malignant transformation, it more often acquires a fibrosarcomatous pattern.[10]

Adequate and or extensive sampling of tissue from the preserved areas is extremely important so as not to miss the histopathological diagnosis. In addition, the paraffin blocks from such cases can be used as positive control blocks whenever Perls stain is contemplated for any other cases.

The microscopic differential diagnoses for schwannoma are Neurofibroma, Perineuroma, Dermatofibroma, Intranodal palisaded myofibroblastoma, if lesion is intranodal and surrounded by a rim of lymphoid tissue, Leiomyoma, Gastrointestinal stromal tumor (if in the GI tract), etc. The anatomic location, histology and immunohistochemistry will help to arrive at the correct diagnosis.

Figure 1: Clinical image of the swelling in upper one-third of right thigh.
1b: Intraoperative image of the swelling.

Fig 2: Smears from fine needle aspiration showed a few benign spindle cells with RBC in the background.
(Pap stain, 40X)

Fig 3a: On gross examination, a smooth greyish white lesion with extensive cystic change on cut surfae was seen. 3b: Cellular Antoni A areas (40X, H&E). 3c: Shows cellular Antoni a areas and Verocay bodies(40X, H&E). 3d: Cystic change and perivascular hyalinisation seen (Black arrow)(40X, H&E).

Fig 4: 4a: Shows cellular Antoni areas and numerous siderophages with golden brown hemosiderin pigment. (40X, H&E stain) 4b: Shows positive Perls stain with blue staining of the hemosiderin pigment. (40X, Perls stain)

Conclusion

Schwannoma with extensive cystic degeneration and hemorrhage should be considered as a differential diagnosis of cystic lesions in the thigh. Spontaneous hemorrhage within a schwannoma can give rise to pain bringing the swelling to the notice of the patient. The histopathological examination remains the mainstay of final diagnosis as ultrasound examination and FNAC may not give a definite preoperative opinion.

Declaration of patient consent: The authors certify that they have obtained all appropriate patient consent forms. In the form, the patient has given his consent for his images and other clinical information to be reported in the journal. The patient understands that his name and initials will not be published and due efforts will be made to conceal his identity, but anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

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